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Data management plan (DMP)

Climate Pavement Performance Analysis

CPPA

Version	Effective date	Description of document/changes
1.0	30/11/2025	First version of the DMP – created for the start of the project

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Start date	2025-11-01
End date	2026-01-01
Funder	COMPANY XY
Funding programme, grant number	To be filled in at a later stage
Internal project number	To be filled in at a later stage

List of acronyms

DMP	data management plan
RDM	research data management
CSV	Comma-Separated-Values (Plain text data format)
PY	Python (Programming language)
IDE	Integrated Developer Environment
CC-BY-4.0	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International
ODC PDDL	Open Data Commons Public Domain Dedication and Licence

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Introduction

Science Europe practical guide, FAIR data

A DMP is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions.

For writing this DMP, we followed [the recommendations of Science Europe](#) as they reflect the guidelines agreed upon by the major funders in Europe.

To make our data FAIR, they generally will be treated according to the following criteria:

- We will make our data findable, by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier and adding relevant metadata.
- We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases, where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests.
- We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain by using the same file formats, schemas and vocabularies. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.
- We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published datasets. The descriptions include details on the methodology used, analytical and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked.

Relevant Policies and Guidelines

- European Commission's document on Ethics and Data Protection: https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/ethics-and-data-protection_he_en.pdf
- Policy for Research Data Management at TU Wien: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Policy%20for%20Research%20Data%20Management.pdf>

1. Data description

1a Lists of datasets that will be reused or produced

Produced datasets

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	Measured_Pavement_Temperature	Structured text	CSV	5 - 10 GB	no
P2	Fourier_Temperature_Model	Source code	PY	100 - 1000 MB	no
P3	Simulated_Pavement_Temperatures	Structured text	CSV	100 - 1000 MB	no

Description for "Measured_Pavement_Temperature" (P1):

Measured pavement temperature data at selected field-testing sites at various subsurface depths are recorded with an acquisition rate of 10 minutes and corresponding timestamps. The dataset is organized into daily CSV files within the dataset directory.

Description for "Fourier_Temperature_Model" (P2):

The Python source code uses measured above ground temperature data from weather stations (usually at 2 meters height) as input to calculate the pavement temperature at various depths. The repository includes a README with usage instructions, licensing, and a requirements.txt for dependencies.

Description for "Simulated_Pavement_Temperatures" (P3):

Simulation outputs generated for cross-validation purposes. This dataset contains pavement temperatures calculated by the *Fourier_Temperature_Model* (P2) using input data from the German validation dataset (R2). It serves to verify model accuracy against established external baselines.

Reused datasets

dataset ID	title	source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	GeoSphere Austria – Messstationen Zehnminutendaten v2	https://doi.org/10.60669/8fya-7x87	CC-BY-4.0	no
R2	DaRkSeit - Temperaturmessdaten	https://data.europa.eu/data/datasets/709786834139254784?locale=en	ODC PDDL	no

Description for "GeoSphere Austria – Messstationen Zehnminutendaten v2" (R1):

The GeoSphere weather station temperature data in a resolution of 10 minutes and a measurement height of 2 m above ground will be used with the `Fourier_Temperature_Model.py` (P2) to calculate the pavement temperatures in various depths. The API parameter for the air temperature 2m is "t1" and the used timeframe is from 01-01-2000 to 01-01-2020 (DD-MM-YYYY).

Description for "DaRkSeit - Temperaturmessdaten" (R2):

The german "DaRkSeit - Temperaturmessdaten" temperature dataset contains reference pavement temperatures. It is used to cross-validate the own measurements (P1) and to benchmark the accuracy of the derived *Fourier_Temperature_Model* (P2).

1b Data generation and reuse

Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

Data Acquisition (P1):

On an instrumented field-testing site, the pavement temperatures at various depths will be recorded with an acquisition rate of 10 minutes. This data is saved locally to a datalogger and automatically synced daily to the TU Wien self-hosted cloud service (TUcloud) in CSV format.

Modelling and Simulation (P2, P3):

The Python model "`Fourier_Temperature_Model.py`" (P2) is developed to calculate pavement subsurface temperatures. It reuses weather station air temperature data from "GeoSphere Austria" (R1) as input variables. The model is trained and calibrated using our own field measurements (P1). The code development is version-controlled via the TU Wien self-hosted TUGitLab instance.

The model generates the "`Simulated_Pavement_Temperatures.csv`" dataset (P3). This output is cross validated with the existing German reference dataset "DaRkSeit" (R2) to verify accuracy.

Preservation and Reuse:

Upon project completion, the final measurement data (archived as ZIP), the production-ready model code, and the validation dataset will all be uploaded to the TU Wien Research Data Repository (DOI: 10.70124/3c1q6-vre62).

2. Documentation and data quality

2a Data organisation, metadata and documentation

The filenames will follow the projects naming convention as defined in chapter “1. Data description”. As no specific metadata standard exists, we rely on a comprehensive documentation strategy. The repository will be structured and organized with a clear folder structure:

- **./P1_Measured_Pavement_Temperature:**
 - Contains daily raw data files following the naming convention “YYMMDD_Measured_Pavement_Temperature.csv” with YYMMDD as start-date timestamp of the measurement.
- **./P2_Fourier_Temperature_Model:**
 - Contains the source code (Fourier_Temperature_Model.py) and the software environment definition (requirements.txt).
- **./P3_Simulated_Pavement_Temperatures:**
 - Contains the validation output data.

Version control is automated via TU Wien selfhosted services: TUCloud (for data) and GitLab (for code) throughout the project duration.

A central README.txt is placed in the root directory. It maps these folders to the DMP IDs, describes the variables (e.g., Depth_cm, Status_Flag), and provides execution instructions for the model.

Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, description or keywords when publishing data in open access repositories. In such a case, we will follow the default template provided by the repository, such as Data Cite Metadata or Dublin Core. As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

2b Data quality control

The data quality will be checked on a multi-stage process when collecting and processing the data:

Measured Data (P1) will be checked automatically for physical plausibility (reasonable temperature range between -20 and +80 °C) to identify malfunctioning sensors. Timestamps are verified for consistency within the 10-minute acquisition rate to detect offsets or missing datapoints.

Code (P2) and simulated temperature data (P3) will be peer-reviewed by project members to ensure proper logical functionality as well as code readability for proper documentation. The simulated output (P3) will be cross validated with the external dataset (R2) by statistical metrics to quantify the model accuracy.

3. Storage and backup during research process

3a Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by Silvio Roth (acting as the person responsible for data management and DMP) in cooperation with the system operator. The data will be stored on the servers of TU Wien.

P1 (Measured_Pavement_Temperature), P3 (Simulated_Pavement_Temperatures):

These datasets will be stored on TUcloud: TUcloud is a sync&share service provided by Campus IT for TU Wien members. It runs on Campus IT servers and offers features known from public cloud systems, such as Dropbox, for example, the exchange of data with authorised persons. Deleted files can be recovered within 180 days.

As additional redundant and robust backup strategy the original raw data also remains on the field datalogger as well as the researchers workstation.

P2 (Fourier_Temperature_Model):

The source code will be developed and stored on TUGitLab with the version control feature to allow for multiple restore points while working on the software.

TUGitLab is an application for managing repositories based on Git provided and managed by Campus IT. Our institute's administrators will manage GitLab groups, assign project permissions, and appoint external project partners as additional GitLab users. This service is highly available and scalable on the Kubernetes platform.

3b Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies listed in the introduction of this document. At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	reading only	reading only
P2	writing	reading only	reading only
P3	writing	reading only	reading only
R1	reading only	reading only	reading only
R2	reading only	reading only	reading only

Selected project members involved in the instrumentation and data acquisition (P1) as well as development of the Python Code (P2, P3) will have full write and read access to the produced datasets. Third-party project partners have read only access to the produced datasets before publishing.

All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team that is maintaining the affected service.

4. Legal and ethical requirements

4a Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

4b Intellectual property rights and rights of use

The following individual(s) hold rights and control access to the project data: Self-produced datasets (P1, P2, P3) are owned by the Research Unit for Road Engineering, Institut of Transportation of TU Wien. Administration and access are controlled by the project coordinator as well as the contact person listed above (see Page 2).

Reused datasets (R1, R2) are owned and controlled by their respective rights holder and owner and are used and cited according to their respective license.

4c Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.

5. Data sharing and long-term preservation

5a Data publication and access conditions

As far as possible, obtained datasets will be published in repositories. Details on access conditions, reuse licenses, reasons for restrictions, etc. are collected in the table below.

dataset ID	access conditions	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open	2025-12-01	TU Wien Research Data	DOI: 10.70124/3c1q6-vre62	CC-BY-4.0
P2	Open	2025-12-01	TU Wien Research Data	DOI: 10.70124/3c1q6-vre62	MIT
P3	Open	2025-12-01	TU Wien Research Data	DOI: 10.70124/3c1q6-vre62	CC-BY-4.0

Repository description:

TU Wien Research Data is an institutional repository of TU Wien to enable storing, sharing and publishing of digital objects, in particular research data. It facilitates the funders' requirements for open access to research data and the FAIR principles by making research output findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. A DOI is assigned to each dataset published in TU Wien Research Data. This service is developed by the TU Wien Center for Research Data Management and hosted by TU.it. <https://researchdata.tuwien.at/>

Methods or software needed to access and use data: All produced datasets (P1, P2, P3) can be viewed and edited with a regular text-editor. For the execution of the Python-Modell "Fourier_Temperature_Model.py" (P3) the programming language Python as well as the listed packages (see "requirements.txt") need to be installed. An Integrated Development Environment (IDE) like Microsoft "VS Code" or JetBrains "PyCharm" are advisable for code and data handling.

5b Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)	foreseeable research uses and/or users
P1	TU Wien Research Data	10 years	Members of the scientific community
P2	TU Wien Research Data	10 years	
P3	TU Wien Research Data	10 years	

6. RDM responsibilities and resources

6a RDM-roles and responsibilities

The Project Coordinator will direct the data management process overall, with the research assistants responsible for ensuring metadata production, day-to-day cross-checks, back-up and other quality control activities are maintained.

6b Resources

There are costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR as outlined below.

cost name	cost type	description	unit	value
Data Management Personnel Costs	Personnel (Data Steward)	Costs for preparing, archiving, providing open access, and subsequent use of research data in repositories. The estimated time for the project data management are 10 hours for the data steward (Univ.Ass. -PraeDoc), resulting in approximately 840€ of costs with 20% Overhead calculation.	EUR	840
Recording and Data Logging	Hardware and Infrastructure	The field-testing recording and data logging device with local storage and internet accessibility for cloud based backup, incurs initial acquisition cost of 7000€.	EUR	7.000
Estimated total costs			EUR	7.840

Coverage of costs:

The costs will be covered by third-party project partners "COMPANY XY" involved in the project.